

Title: Machine Learning, Machine Vision and Robot Vision will be at the top of Robotics developers' priorities in 2018

Name: Ali Sina

Affiliation: UCI Applied Innovation Lab (UC Irvine)

INTRODUCTION: Machines can learn in a variety of different ways and it seems like every day there's a new stealth learning methodology in the works but Machine Vision involves more than just computer algorithms; engineers and roboticists also have to account for camera hardware that allow robots to process physical data. Robot vision is very closely linked to machine vision, which can be given credit for the emergence of robot guidance and automatic inspection systems. Robots can physically affect their environment.

AIM: An influx of big data i.e. visual information available on the web (including annotated/labeled photos and videos) has propelled advances in computer vision, which in turn has helped further machine-learning based structured prediction learning techniques leading to robot vision applications like identification and sorting of objects.

MATERIALS AND METHODS: Anomaly detection with unsupervised learning, such as building systems capable of finding and assessing faults in silicon wafers using convolutional neural networks. Extrasensory technologies like radar, LIDAR, and ultrasound are also driving the development of 360-degree vision-based systems for autonomous vehicles and drones.

RESULTS: Machine learning and robotics is at the top of developers' priorities for 2018, with 69.4 percent stating that they're building robotics apps and 48.7 percent of all developers indicating the use of machine learning in their projects. And it will continue to be a top priority.

CONCLUSIONS: Machine Learning will remain a long-term priority in robotics due to military contract, massive investments by a barrage of auto-manufacturers, "Drone mania", a whole new wave of Ai start-ups and innovations quantum scaled by major robotics manufacturers.

KEYWORDS: Machine Learning, Robotics, Machine Vision, Robot Vision, Supervises Learning

BIOGRAPHY: Ali Sina is a five-time entrepreneur, fund manager and keynote speaker at big data, robotics and AI conferences worldwide. He is currently working on next generation AI solutions at UCI Applied Innovation lab. Ali is the Founder and CEO of Forkaia – an accelerator of independent data scientists and programmers who use the Forkaia freelancing platform to work on ai projects they find interesting. We're building the ecosystem of the future and birthing companies that are positioned to fundamentally change existing markets and create new ones. Our network consists of the most talented engineers and scientists worldwide collaborating and working on some of the most interesting and groundbreaking projects on the planet. Our culture is built around collaboration, experimentation and disruption. We give money, support and resources to the projects we like and tend to incubate a lot of our own ideas. We use the Forkaia ecosystem for constant experimentation and incubate, accelerate and hold a portfolio of our own start-ups.

Current Portfolio includes:

INSOLAR – technology company that connects solar customers with the best solar panel installers at the lowest prices in the market using Artificial Intelligence.

Rise Capital – a Blockchain and Cryptoasset Investment Fund using ai. We're taking your savings to the next level...even your spare change.

Moo.V.Room – IoT-AI-Laced Immersive Entertainment Experiences. Why would you want to watch a movie when you can enter one.

Side Hustle – Smartphone App for side money gigs

We believe in sharing & give equity to our programmers on the projects they work on through Round Z Ventures.

We're always interested in disruptive, creative minds - passionate problem-solvers & motivated individuals who are interested on working on projects that are shaping our future. Visit www.Forkaia.com for employment